

THE LEVEL OF PROPHILE CYTOKINES IN CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS IN CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10894804>

Topicality. It is known that humoral mechanisms occupy an important place in the maintenance and regulation of homeostasis of mucous membrane of nose of paranasal sinuses [1, 2]. Cooperation of immune competent cells mediated by cytokines is of special importance together with known multi grade multi factor sides of immune response to an infectious agent [3, 4].

Chronic rhinosinusitis with nasal polyps (CRSwNP) or without nasal polyps (CRSsNP) are inflammatory diseases of the nasal mucosa and paranasal sinuses [5, 7]. In this review, we focus on CRSwNP that affects 4% of the general population. Symptoms are related to the bilateral and multifocal development of polyps and include nasal obstruction, hyposmia, discharge and facial pain or pressure, which lasts for at least 3 months and causes substantially impaired quality of life [6, 8]. Medical treatment is based on topical or systemic corticosteroids. Surgery is performed in patients having failed well-conducted medical treatment. Although effective, surgery does not prevent recurrence of symptoms related to polyp regrowth [9]. Recent biotherapies, including anti-IgE, anti-IL-5 and anti-IL-4R α , are of demonstrated effectiveness, and their use has grown exponentially [10].

Typical histological features of nasal polyps include inflammation of type 2 T-helper cells (Th2) accompanied by major tissue remodeling (thickening of basement membrane, hyperplasia of the epithelium, fibrosis) [11]. The dense inflammatory infiltrate is composed of several immune cell types such as T and B lymphocytes, group 2 innate lymphoid cells (ILC2), eosinophils and neutrophils, mast cells and macrophages [12, 13]. The cytokines produced by these immune cells and a number of other cells (epithelial cells or fibroblasts) play a central role in the pathogenesis of inflammatory diseases, including CRSwNP [14]. Cytokines are key factors generating and modulating cell-to-cell communication in immunological responses, hematopoietic development as well as host responses to infectious agents and inflammatory stimuli [15].

Objective: assessment of self-descriptiveness of the amount of prophile cytokines in children with chronic rhinosinusitis with various etiologies.

Materials and methods. The research was based on the data of examination of 86 children with chronic rhinosinusitis in the age from 3 to 17 years old. Among these patients there were 34 boys and 54 girls, the average age

of the patients was 9.5 ± 3.75 years old. The data of 20 practically healthy children served to be the control. Definition of the production of interleukins (IL- 1β , IL-4, IL-8) in the studied patterns (blood serum) with the help of solid-phase enzyme immunoassay.

Results of the research and discussion. The results of measurement of cytokines concentration in blood serum of the children showed that, in spite of notable heterogeneity of the obtained results in each group, children with chronic rhinosinusitis with bacterial etiology had increase of IL-6 and IL-8 compared with the children of the control group ($p < 0.05$), and a tendency for an increase of IL-4 amount.

Analysis of the concentrations of pro and anti-inflammatory cytokines correlation in children with CRS did not reveal significant differences between etiologic factors, testifying untype of inflammatory process progression. Though more decreased concentration of pro and anti-inflammatory cytokines was registered in children with polyposis, and the highest one in children with fungal CRS.

Conclusions: children with CRS independent of the etiological factor had significant alterations of the inflammatory mediators complex depending on the expression of the inflammatory process in paranasal sinuses.

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